

Evaluation of the requirements of a proposed multimodal framework for user experience evaluation

Online form (Google Forms) — English version

Informed Consent Form (ICF)

Research Title: A Proposal for a Multimodal Framework for User Experience Evaluation in Interactive Web Systems

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Purpose

You are being invited to participate in this research, whose purpose is to evaluate the specification and implementation of 14 requirements for a multimodal framework for User Experience (UX) evaluation in interactive Web systems. Please read carefully what follows and ask the researchers in case of any doubt.

Research Participants

The target population of the research is composed of professionals from academia and industry with experience in the areas of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and Software Engineering (SE).

Study Procedure

This study is a focus group and will consist of two stages:

In the first stage, participants must inform their availability for conducting the focus group. Next, they fill out a profile characterization questionnaire and a form for the evaluation of the framework's requirements, so that participants can, in advance, make their considerations about the material that will be discussed in the focus group. This form presents the list of the 14 requirements to be evaluated through the Perspective-Based Reading (PBR) technique, which uses checklists for the inspection of software requirements, in which different stakeholder perspectives, such as developers, testers, and end users, are used to identify defects, such as omission, ambiguity, incorrect information, extraneous information, and inconsistency.

In the second stage, participants will meet remotely, on a previously agreed date and time, through the Google Meet platform, to discuss each one's impressions of the list of requirements. As informed in the ICF, the session will be recorded and will have a maximum duration of 90 minutes. In the first part, the researchers will give a presentation about the framework and the implemented requirements to clarify possible doubts of the participants. In the second part, participants may freely discuss their perceptions regarding the requirements and the framework.

Upon reaching the maximum time, or upon exhausting the discussion topics, the focus group will be concluded.

Involvement in the Research

By participating in this study you will allow the researcher to gather information regarding your profile and your knowledge about HCI and SE, through questionnaires and the focus group. You are free to refuse to participate and also to refuse to continue participating at any stage of the research, without any prejudice. Whenever you wish, you may request more information about the research through the project's emails and, if necessary, through the email of the Research Ethics Committee.

Risks and Discomfort

Participation in this research does not entail legal complications. The research will be controlled and all participant information will be kept confidential, especially each participant's responses to the questionnaires, their identity, and their personal information. To ensure the confidentiality of participants' information, only their responses and demographic information will be used for the preparation of scientific articles intended for publication in journals and events. The procedures adopted in this research comply with the Criteria for Ethics in Research with Human Beings according to Resolution No. 196/96 of the National Health Council. None of the procedures used pose risks to your dignity. In case of fatigue or any other type of discomfort during any of the stages of the study, the participant may stop participating at any time, without any prejudice.

Recording

By participating in this research, I agree with the recording and transcription of the audio of the focus group to be conducted on the Google Meet platform, allowing the researchers to use excerpts of my responses during the evaluation of the framework's requirements. We reinforce that all participant information will be kept in absolute confidentiality. The results will subsequently be presented in aggregate form, so that a participant is not associated with a specific datum, ensuring your anonymity during the dissemination of the results.

Confidentiality

All information collected in this study is strictly confidential and only the researchers will have knowledge of it. All data will be stored in a Google Drive repository for a minimum period of 5 years.

Benefits

By participating in this research you will not have any direct benefit. However, we hope that this study brings important information about UX evaluation research, so that the knowledge that will be built from this research may contribute benefits to the UX evaluation process in interactive Web systems. The researchers commit to disseminating the results obtained.

Payment

You will not have any type of expense to participate in this research, nor will anything be paid for your participation. In case of need to obtain an Internet connection, we may provide a stipend of up to R\$30.00, provided it is requested in advance.

After these clarifications, we request your free consent to participate in this research.

2. In view of the items presented above, I, freely and with clarification, express my consent to participate in the research and authorize the conduct of the research and the disclosure of the data obtained in this study. *

Mark only one oval.

I agree

I do not agree

Requirements Evaluation

This evaluation is an extension of the article “A Proposal for a Multimodal Framework for User Experience Evaluation in Interactive Web Systems” (Zacarias et al., 2024), whose objective was to identify the requirements and propose a multimodal framework for UX evaluation in interactive Web systems, making it more comprehensive for different domains. The requirements were elicited through documental analysis of previous UX evaluation studies of this research group, using open coding. The 14 elicited requirements were then used for the initial design of the multimodal framework, including guidelines, tools, and artifacts for monitoring and processing the collected UX data.

Table 1 presents the 14 requirements (identified from R1 to R14) elicited from the analysis of the seven previous UX evaluation studies (Zacarias et al., 2024). Details about the coding of each requirement are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10878937>.

Figure 1 illustrates the proposed model for the framework architecture, which must contain a set of integrated tools for UX evaluation, following requirements (R1 to R14).

Table 1. Requirements elicited for the proposed multimodal framework.

ID	REQUIREMENT	CLASSIFICATION
R1	The framework must allow the user to systematically identify, extract, quantify, and analyze affective states and subjective information.	Functional
R2	The framework must provide the user with computational intelligence models, in order to enable greater automation and complexity in UX evaluation.	Functional
R3	The framework must allow the user to access, organize, and modify their collected data through a manageable database.	Functional
R4	The framework must allow the user to perform the collection, organization, and processing of interaction data.	Functional
R5	The framework must provide the user with a set of self-report questionnaire templates that can be adapted to different domains, following guidelines for UX evaluation.	Functional
R6	The framework must allow the user to capture voice interaction traces, transcribing the spoken content.	Functional
R7	The framework must allow the user to capture mouse interaction traces.	Functional
R8	The framework must allow the user to capture eye movements during interactions.	Functional
R9	The framework must allow the user to capture keyboard input data during interactions.	Functional
R10	The framework must allow the user to generate reports through indicators that enable documenting the UX evaluation.	Functional
R11	The framework must allow the user to select which traces should be tracked during interactions.	Functional
R12	The framework must allow the user to perform evolutionary maintenance.	Non-functional
R13	The framework must allow the user to access it free of charge for consultation, examination, modification, and redistribution.	Non-functional
R14	The framework must allow the user to create charts for visualization of the processed data.	Functional

Figure 1. Proposed model for the multimodal framework.

Note: the diagram below preserves the original (Portuguese) labels from the validated study figure. The following key gives the English translation of each label.

English label	Original label (in figure)
USER	USUÁRIO
EVALUATION SCRIPT	ROTEIRO DE AVALIAÇÃO
BROWSER PLUGIN	PLUGIN NO NAVEGADOR
VOICE	VOZ
EYE	OLHO
HISTORY	HISTÓRICO
KEYBOARD	TECLADO
MOUSE	MOUSE
EMOTION	EMOÇÃO
USER REGISTRATION	CADASTRO DO USUÁRIO
MULTIMODAL CAPTURE TOOL	FERRAMENTA DE CAPTURA MULTIMODAL
COLLECTION REPORT	RELATÓRIO DE COLETA
DATABASE	BANCO DE DADOS
DATA PROCESSING	TRATAMENTO DOS DADOS
DATA ANALYSIS	ANÁLISE DE DADOS
Fuzzy Logic / Classification / Clustering	Lógica Fuzzy / Classificação / Clusterização
FINAL ANALYSIS	ANÁLISE FINAL
SELF-REPORT TOOL	FERRAMENTA DE AUTORRELATO
SET OF GUIDELINES	CONJUNTO DE DIRETRIZES
QUESTIONNAIRE	QUESTIONÁRIO

Description of the proposed model for the multimodal framework architecture

The framework architecture is centered on three main artifacts: a multimodal capture tool, an evaluation script, and a self-report tool with a set of guidelines that guide the evaluation of Web interfaces, considering, initially, aspects of accessibility, usability, and information transparency. The multimodal capture and self-report tools were developed in previous research projects and, in this framework, will start to operate in an integrated manner. The sequence diagram of the framework can also be consulted at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10878937>.

To use the framework, researcher and designer users must register, in order to store the collected data in a database integrated with the tools (R3 and R4). To build their UX evaluation

script, the user may consult a list of guidelines related to UX evaluation (e.g. accessibility, usability, and information transparency), and define which tasks will be performed by the participants and which aspects will be evaluated. With the evaluation script prepared, the user may choose between using only the multimodal capture tool, only the self-report tool, or both tools in an integrated manner.

The multimodal capture tool will allow the user to choose which interaction data they wish to track: voice, eye movement, navigation history, keyboard, mouse, or expressed emotion (R1, R6, R7, R8, R9, and R11). Selection options will be provided in the tool's interface, and participants' permission must be requested for this tracking. The self-report data collection tool will allow the user to select different types of questionnaires to evaluate emotional responses to the computational solution, based on the perception of the study participants (R5). The user will have access to several data analysis techniques, such as fuzzy logic, classification, and clustering (R2), to generate charts (R14) and detailed reports about the interaction (R10), facilitating the final UX analysis in the research.

The elicited requirements do not limit the framework's functionalities, allowing the addition of new UX evaluation techniques and methods in the future (R12). The proposal also aims at open-source distribution and free access, fostering a collaborative community for modification, improvement, and maintenance (R13). Thus, the multimodal framework may help researchers in various environments, providing accessible tools and facilitating the planning and conduct of UX studies with different types of users. With several evaluation artifacts in a single environment, the study protocols can be quickly adapted to different contexts.

Requirements evaluation method

Considering the description of the elicitation, the specification, and the implementation proposal presented, we invite you to evaluate the list of the 14 requirements using the Perspective-Based Reading (PBR) technique.

The PBR technique is based on the inspection of software requirements, in which different stakeholder perspectives, such as developers, testers, and end users, are used to identify defects. Each perspective has specific checklists, ensuring greater coverage and precision in the detection of failures. The method can be supported by tools that promote standardization and efficiency (Freitas et al., 2004; Wholin et al., 2024).

Types of Evaluation in the Form:

For each selected requirement, you must analyze whether it is possible to identify the following types of defects:

- **Omission:** Absence of essential information or requirements needed for understanding or implementing the system.
- **Ambiguity:** Presence of terms or expressions that allow multiple interpretations, compromising the clarity of the requirement.
- **Incorrect Information:** Data, details, or specifications that are wrong or do not reflect the reality of the system or domain.
- **Extraneous Information:** Inclusion of elements or requirements unrelated to the scope or objective of the system, being irrelevant or unnecessary.

- **Inconsistency:** Conflict or contradiction between different requirements or parts of the document, compromising the coherence of the system.

If no problem is identified, you may select the option "I did not find any defects". After analyzing each requirement, there will also be a field for the evaluator to leave additional comments, if desired.

8. R1. The framework must allow the user to systematically identify, extract, quantify, and analyze affective states and subjective information. *

Functional requirement

Mark all that apply.

- Omission
- Ambiguity
- Incorrect Information
- Extraneous Information
- Inconsistency
- I did not find any defects

9. Comment your evaluation (optional)

10. R2. The framework must provide the user with computational intelligence models, in order to enable greater automation and complexity in UX evaluation. *

Functional requirement

Mark all that apply.

- Omission
- Ambiguity
- Incorrect Information
- Extraneous Information
- Inconsistency
- I did not find any defects

11. Comment your evaluation (optional)

12. R3. The framework must allow the user to access, organize, and modify their collected data through a manageable database. *

Functional requirement

Mark all that apply.

- Omission
- Ambiguity
- Incorrect Information
- Extraneous Information
- Inconsistency
- I did not find any defects

13. Comment your evaluation (optional)

14. R4. The framework must allow the user to perform the collection, organization, and processing of interaction data. *

Functional requirement

Mark all that apply.

- Omission
- Ambiguity
- Incorrect Information

- Extraneous Information
- Inconsistency
- I did not find any defects

15. Comment your evaluation (optional)

16. R5. The framework must provide the user with a set of self-report questionnaire templates that can be adapted to different domains, following guidelines for UX evaluation. *

Functional requirement

Mark all that apply.

- Omission
- Ambiguity
- Incorrect Information
- Extraneous Information
- Inconsistency
- I did not find any defects

17. Comment your evaluation (optional)

18. R6. The framework must allow the user to capture voice interaction traces, transcribing the spoken content. *

Functional requirement

Mark all that apply.

- Omission
- Ambiguity
- Incorrect Information
- Extraneous Information
- Inconsistency
- I did not find any defects

19. Comment your evaluation (optional)

20. R7. The framework must allow the user to capture mouse interaction traces. *

Functional requirement

Mark all that apply.

- Omission
- Ambiguity
- Incorrect Information
- Extraneous Information
- Inconsistency
- I did not find any defects

21. Comment your evaluation (optional)

22. R8. The framework must allow the user to capture eye movements during interactions. *

Functional requirement

Mark all that apply.

- Omission
- Ambiguity
- Incorrect Information
- Extraneous Information
- Inconsistency
- I did not find any defects

23. Comment your evaluation (optional)

24. R9. The framework must allow the user to capture keyboard input data during interactions. *

Functional requirement

Mark all that apply.

- Omission
- Ambiguity
- Incorrect Information
- Extraneous Information
- Inconsistency
- I did not find any defects

25. Comment your evaluation (optional)

26. R10. The framework must allow the user to generate reports through indicators that enable documenting the UX evaluation. *

Functional requirement

Mark all that apply.

- Omission
- Ambiguity
- Incorrect Information
- Extraneous Information
- Inconsistency
- I did not find any defects

27. Comment your evaluation (optional)

28. R11. The framework must allow the user to select which traces should be tracked during interactions. *

Functional requirement

Mark all that apply.

- Omission
- Ambiguity
- Incorrect Information

- Extraneous Information
- Inconsistency
- I did not find any defects

29. Comment your evaluation (optional)

30. R12. The framework must allow the user to perform evolutionary maintenance. *

Non-functional requirement

Mark all that apply.

- Omission
- Ambiguity
- Incorrect Information
- Extraneous Information
- Inconsistency
- I did not find any defects

31. Comment your evaluation (optional)

32. R13. The framework must allow the user to access it free of charge for consultation, examination, modification, and redistribution. *

Non-functional requirement

Mark all that apply.

- Omission
- Ambiguity
- Incorrect Information
- Extraneous Information
- Inconsistency
- I did not find any defects

33. Comment your evaluation (optional)

34. R14. The framework must allow the user to create charts for visualization of the processed data. *

Functional requirement

Mark all that apply.

- Omission
- Ambiguity
- Incorrect Information
- Extraneous Information
- Inconsistency
- I did not find any defects

35. Comment your evaluation (optional)

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